

EnergyMeasures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D4.2

Report on energy consumption of participating households, updated

 <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

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February 2024

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About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMeasures is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This document is an updated report on changes to energy consumption of the EnergyMeasures participating households over the life of the project. A brief overview is provided for each country, outlining the most important energy sources and energy-related challenges, the number of households recruited, characteristics of dwellings, and information about energy use, household composition, etc. The approach to measuring the reductions in energy consumption is outlined for each focal country and the annualised 'savings' for the different types of energy is then detailed and discussed.

Glossary

BCR	Brussels capital region
DoA	Description of Action
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene
ESRI	Economic and Social Research Institute
FEBEG	Federatie van de Belgische Elektriciteits- en Gasbedrijven
LPG	Liquid Petroleum Gas
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PEF	Primary energy factor
PM10	Particulates of a size less than 10 μm
POPD	Protection of personal data
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEAI	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and context

The EnergyMeasures Horizon 2020 project implemented coordinated household energy engagement programmes and worked to address structural issues surrounding energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, and the United Kingdom. Engaging energy poor households comprised the core component of the project, in this respect the project partners worked with such households to reduce their energy vulnerability through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in their energy-related practices.

During Task 2.2 key indicators that characterise those most at-risk of energy poverty were mapped out, and energy poor and at-risk households were recruited. Then, for Task 2.3 householders were provided with low-cost energy measures and supported to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that both took account of the nature of their dwellings and was reflective of the lived experience of the household members.

This document is an update of a report arising from the monitoring and quantifying the impact of Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 activities related to energy consumption. While the focus on this report is on avoided energy consumption – so called ‘energy savings’, there are also other consumption related metrics of interest, which will be addressed in so far as possible. These include trends in consumption of electrical energy and thermal energy, and the reduction in people living in energy poverty. A earlier This report comprises the description of the baseline against which so-called ‘energy savings’; changes in electrical energy demand, thermal energy demand and reductions of people living in energy poverty will be measured throughout the project.

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic had a serious impact on gaining access to households, causing substantial delays in household recruitment and engagement. The delays and disruption caused by Covid-19 pandemic meant that household recruitment originally scheduled to commence in March 2021, only really started in January 2022 and that it continued long after it originally was envisaged to conclude. Indeed, the engagements and data collection proceeded at different schedules reflecting local specificities (particularly in response to the pandemic and its aftermath).

This report consists of nine sections. This introductory section provides context and background and gives an overview of the document, and it presents an overview of the approach taken in data collection, describing the rationale for the approach taken, while noting and explaining any differences arising from each country's context. Sections 2 to 8 present the approaches to data collection relating to energy consumption in each of the seven focal countries. To provide context, this section includes a brief overview of the major energy sources and energy-related challenges within each country. Then it focuses on the individual strategies for data collection followed, as well as generalised data, such as energy sources and heating systems used in each country, characteristics of the households visited, main challenges and opportunities and initial analysis of lessons learned for iteration purposes. Lastly, Section 9 offers some conclusions based on the results presented.

1.2 Note on methodology

This report reports on the calculation of key metrics relating to energy in participating households over the duration of the household energy engagement programmes, namely: so-called “energy savings”; changes in electrical energy demand and thermal energy demand; reductions of people in energy poverty. To achieve this goal, the task involved defining a baseline figure against which energy savings could be measured, where possible for each participating household, otherwise in the form of the average consumption for a typical household in each local action. A standard idealised approach to, and criteria for, measuring energy savings was devised by partners. This approach – assuming the availability of, and access to, data – calculated energy consumption using utility bills and/or remote measurement for each household at the outset of the project, and periodically over the course of the engagement. Where data was not accessible, the preferred option involved using a representative sample of households in each community.

While a standardised approach would be preferable, the reality was that partners in each country were dealing with very different circumstances. The focal countries were very diverse. Equally diverse are the weather patterns, the energy landscape, the energy sources available, the building stock, and the household compositions. Cultural and social differences not only play an important role in the experience and use of energy, but also in the willingness to share data. Bureaucracy and processes play a part too. Access to current and historic data can be reached in some cases only through personal approval, while in others information can be accessed collectively or through smart devices. Contracts, energy bills and the information available on them also vary widely. These differences became more and more apparent once partners moved to an accelerated pace of engagement. In this task, it was therefore deemed important to provide differentiated strategies and approaches, to ensure that the outputs of the EnergyMeasures project are meaningful and provide guidelines for replication within its own boundaries, as well as maximising the potential of trans-regional inspiration.

Project partners measured energy savings achieved over the duration of the EnergyMeasures project using, where available, historic data from participating households, and other available anonymised consumption data, and assess what proportion of these are being used to increase comfort and minimise rebound effects. Data on energy consumption (energy bills, fuel receipts, estimates of *ad hoc* purchases, *etc.*) was collected from participating householders. This document builds upon (and represents an update of) an earlier report, which considered baseline data for households.¹ Using as much ‘real’ data as possible (*e.g.*, sourced from invoices, utility data, *etc.*), and where necessary extrapolating from representative and other proxy data. Calculated energy savings were presented in terms of primary energy each of the seven focal countries. A primary energy factor (PEF) of 1.9 was used for electricity as outlined in Directive (EU) 2023/179, Article 31. Natural gas was converted to primary energy using a PEF of 1.2. While a default primary energy factor of 1.1 used for other non-renewables (*e.g.*, coal) and 0.2 for renewables (*e.g.*, biomass).

¹ See D4.1 ‘Initial report on energy consumption of participating households’ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400852>

2 Belgium

2.1 Country overview – Belgium

2.1.1 Energy Poverty in Belgium

More than one in five Belgian households were in energy poverty in 2021 (20.6%) with this share only slightly changing since 2009 (Meyer & Coene 2023). However, as shown in Figure 1 there are strong differences between the regions. In 2021, Flanders has the lowest rate of energy poverty at 14.8% of households. Wallonia had the highest rate at 28.8%, with the Brussels Capital Region close behind with 27.4% of households in energy poverty (Meyer & Coene 2023). In Flanders, this equates to almost one million people affected by energy poverty.

Figure 1: Percentage of the population living in energy poverty by region, Belgium 2021 (data from Meyer & Coene 2023)

According to Meyer & Coene (2023), the majority (more than 60%) of energy-poor households are single people or single-parent families. Women and seniors are more affected by energy poverty. Women are over-represented in the households most vulnerable to energy poverty. 16.1% of Belgian women live in a household that suffers from energy poverty, compared to 13.7% of men. While some 26.0% of people over 65 suffer from energy poverty, compared to just 11.6% of 18- to 49-year-olds. There are also twice as many renters as owners who are affected by energy poverty. Households in poor-quality housing are more affected by energy poverty. 21.2% of households in energy poverty lived in a home with defects in 2021, compared to 13.3% of households that are not in energy poverty.

Although households with no income from employment are more at risk of energy poverty (38% of such households are energy poor), there are 14.4% of households with employment who experience energy poverty. One-third of people in energy poverty also live in poor housing conditions: they live in non-insulated houses, suffer from mould and damp or have inadequate sanitary facilities. The main causes of energy poverty are insufficient income, poor housing quality, and rising energy prices. Additional reinforcing factors are a low level of education, a small social network, low technical skills and a lack of access to the necessary information and services. Energy poverty has many consequences, which make the situation even more complex. Households in energy poverty have more health problems, more frequent housing costs, difficulties in school or work, debt and suffer from social isolation. In recent years, we have seen an increase in electricity prices, as well as in the number of payment instalment plans with energy suppliers.

There are several social housing companies active in Belgium, but the share of social housing is still far too small to cope with the social housing shortage. The waiting time for a social house is 4 years on average and is still rising. As a result, a large proportion of families with the lowest incomes are forced to rent on the private rental market. Here demand far exceeds supply, forcing many poorer tenants to live in substandard housing. The quality of the homes in which the lowest income households live is below average in several respects: less or no insulation, more frequent moisture problems, less space, less comfort, and hardly any renewable energy sources (Heylen & Vanderstraeten 2019).

The government offers various forms of support to energy-poor households. For instance, there is a social tariff for gas and electricity (and water), but the conditions for eligibility are quite strict, and its target group does not cover the entire segment of poor households (FOD Economie, 2021). In addition, there is an annual heating allowance for poor households that heat with fuel oil or petroleum. There is also an energy fund, from which households experiencing difficulties in paying their energy bills can receive an additional allowance, but this is a favour and not a right, and its allocation is rather exceptional. Both the government and the network manager of gas and electricity also offer various premiums for owners who renovate their house or make it more energy efficient (Wonen-Vlaanderen, 2021). However, these premiums do not apply to landlords in the private rental market. Also, for poor owners these premiums are not sufficient to cover the costs of a renovation.

2.1.2 Energy sources in Belgium

As shown in Figure 2, Belgium is still heavily dependent on nuclear energy (grey), imported mostly from France, and fossil fuels (red), evident in the dashboard below. Renewable energy (green) has still a lot of potential for growth but requires serious investment.

Figure 2: Total fuel mix in Flanders 2020 (VREG)

In 2020, 35.8% of the electricity supplied came from renewable energy sources. Hydropower (17.8%) was the most important renewable energy source, followed by onshore wind power (5.5%) and biomass from agriculture or forestry (3.6%). The largest share of renewable energy came from Flanders itself (7.2%).

In addition, France (5.6%) and Norway (5.3%) were the most important import countries for renewable energy. In 2020, 32.6% of the electricity supplied came from nuclear sources (grey) and 31.5% from fossil fuels (red). As shown in Figure 3, Belgian electricity consumption was 80.87 TWh in 2020, rising to 83.66 TWh in 2021.

Figure 3: Electricity consumption in Belgium (FEBEG, 2021)

Figure 4: Distribution of electricity consumption, in TWh, by market segment, Belgium 2020 (FEBEG 2021)

In 2020, 23% of final ‘observed’ energy consumption was by households, compared to 45.2% by industry (Figure 4).

In recent years, there has been an argument that we should all share the burden for ‘loading the network’. The figures presented above as Figure 4, however show that households pay a disproportionate share in network costs and taxation, while industry usually also profits from preferential pricing. Belgium is a densely populated country, heavily industrialised, with a capitalised focus north and socially focused south. Whether these differences will be resolved remains to be seen.

2.1.3 Belgian energy-related challenges

Throughout the last years, Belgium has failed several times to reach the commitments agreed at the European level. Several climate dossiers have gone back to the drawing board. The complex composition of governments (federal, regional, municipal) and the often-unstable political situation, makes governmental agreements difficult. A difficult to reach decision back in 2003 to withdraw from nuclear energy was largely motivated by the high risks associated with this form of energy, particularly the risk of accidents and proliferation. Since 2003, however, no government had made it a priority to properly plan an outline for the 'nuclear exit'. The most recent federal government (minister from the Green party) took radical steps towards the nuclear exit, but then the War in Ukraine came and the surrounding volatility and uncertainty in the energy market which caused extreme price surges. This in turn provided arguments for lobbyists who warned of the dangers of energy supply and potential blackouts from a nuclear exit. However, the only salvageable nuclear power-plants in Belgium only provide 2-3% of the total energy supply. Their inflexibility in the face of the rapidly changing energy market and transition to electrification is still not enough to place them outside of the energy realm.

Belgium (as other European countries) has and will continue to feel the knock-on consequences of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Energy prices saw a record high in March 2022. For the time being there is no impact on the Belgian supply of natural gas. Belgium is a hub for gas supplies to the European Union but has a very small share of Russian gas for its own consumption (6%). In the meantime, the energy giants do not appear to be shying away from profit taking. *"Thanks to the energy crisis, in 2021 Belgian gas-fired power stations will have made the highest profits in fifteen years. In total, these could amount to €353 m. This is what a new report by the federal energy regulator reveals"* (Van Horenbeek 2022). In 2021, Engie, the French parent company of the previously Belgian Electrabel, made €3.7b profit, thanks to – among other things – high electricity and gas prices. Engie, also did very good business in the first quarter of 2022 thanks to high energy prices. Operating profit rose 75 per cent compared with the result for the first three months of 2021. The biggest profit drivers were the Belgian nuclear power plants and the gas trading business. Of the total €3.53b operating profit, €583m came from these nuclear power plants and €520m from the natural gas trading business. Engie has raised its net profit forecast for 2022 sharply from between €3.1b and €3.3b to between €3.8b and €4.4b (Sertyn 2022). Engie, is now demanding from the Belgian the government - and thus the taxpayer - to help pay for the disposal of additional nuclear waste. *"This is totally unacceptable, according to Bond Beter Leefmilieu, Greenpeace and Inter Environnement Wallonie. Because what does the Belgian get in exchange for these sky-high costs? The nuclear extension does not contribute to security of supply or lower energy prices"* (Clarysse 2022). Opponents of nuclear power argue that keeping the last 2 nuclear power-plants open with the associated renovation and maintenance costs, could prevent Belgium from properly investing in renewable energy sources and retrofits in a large scale, such as for wind turbines at sea.

2.2 Participating households – Belgium

2.2.1 Background

The Belgian cluster, comprised of SAAMO and Kamp C, had a target to engage 500 energy poor households. They faced significant challenges in recruiting households. As with all partners the Covid-19 pandemic directly impacted on outreach activities. Moreover, the pandemic placed unforeseen demands on the resources of the organisations that had been factored in as key collaborators in their engagement strategy and from which it was expected the bulk of referrals would come (City Region of Turnhout and Turnhout OCMW – Openbaar centrum voor maatschappelijk welzijn²). Accordingly, and as reported in the interim report on energy consumption³, recruitment was extremely slow in Belgium in the first years of this project – even more so than partners in other countries⁴. Indeed, as of April 2022, just 35 households have been recruited to the project in Belgium. Following deliberation and discussions with other partners, the SAAMO and Kamp C revised their approach to engagement, maintaining existing activities but also in particular developing a collaboration with *Energiesnoeiers* ('energy cutters') which visit families to conduct energy scans and give tips on how they can save energy in their home. This resulted in a significant increase in engagement, with finally a figure of 598 households engaged by the project – surpassing the initial target by 20%. Albeit the slow start meant that many of these households were recruited in the later part of the project.

2.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

Belgian households participating in the project have been recruited from Turnhout, a medium-sized city in the province of Antwerp, in northern Belgium, in the region of Flanders. The city is very close to the border with the Netherlands. Turnhout, which has c. 45,000 inhabitants is at first sight a typical small Flanders municipality, it has, however, a surprisingly high percentage of poverty in comparison to others. The recruited households are very diverse, they include single parents, old people, singles, immigrants with small or large families. Most dwellings have been either terraced housing or apartments.

Figure 5 on the following page shows typical apartment blocks in Turnhout from the 1970s, many of which have been waiting for energy retrofitting for several years already. While the photos in Figure 6 show detached brick housing typical of some of the participating households in Turnhout. These are reflective of the condition of the housing stock in the private market, where households in poverty are often circulating for years: with common issues such as: mould (see also Figure 7), poor quality double-glazing, with often insufficiently insulated walls and roofs.

² Public Centre for Social Welfare

³ See D4.1 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400852>

⁴ Which of course also faced many challenges arising from the pandemic.

Figure 5: Typical apartment blocks in Turnhout dating from the 1970s.

Figure 6: Typical detached brick houses in Turnhout.

Figure 7: Mould due to poor ventilation, insufficient heating and/or cold bridges.

The recruited dwellings are typically built from brick and often are in very poor condition, with old windows and doors, poor (if any) insulation, and old inefficient boilers. Some homes are in dire condition, but householders are clearly doing their best they can with the little they have. Of those recruited households surveyed, one in three received support to pay their energy bills. Householder raised a range of issues – just over 35% said their home was too cold in winter; over 40% reported being too warm in summer; nearly 35% said there were draughts; 20% raised air quality; almost 30% complained about moulds and condensation; about 9% had leaks; and 17% reported other issues.

2.3 Energy consumption data – Belgium

Table 1: Participating households - Belgium

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Natural Gas	325	0
Electricity	122	0
Heating oil	112	0
Renewable energy	36	0

Total # households	598	Average # residents	2.58
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There were several issues collecting data in Belgium. At the beginning of the project, attempts were made to enrol participating households in the open-source platform EnergyID for monthly meter readings. Unfortunately, it was not possible to take advantage of this due to GDPR restrictions. Due to GDPR restrictions, it also proved not possible to obtain meter readings from energy suppliers or the grid operator. Miscommunications with Energiesnoeiers at the start of their collaboration resulted in issues associated with energy data including non-collection. SAAMO & Kamp C also tried to gather data from the participating households through surveys. Unfortunately, there was a low response rate to the survey and much of the collected information was unusable due to a large-scale changeover to digital meters, and possible incorrect data collection, which made meter readings practically incomparable. All of this was compounded by the fact that the Belgian partners were busy working to ‘catch-up’ with respect to household recruitment, which meant that these issues were not fully apparent until very late in the proceedings. As a result, the Belgian partners have supplemented the small amount of real data they have from householders with use of regional household energy data from Flanders to estimate energy trends amongst participating households. While this is not an ideal scenario, its impact is perhaps ironically reduced by the fact that more generally households have significantly reduced their energy consumption during this period. All of which makes it extremely difficult (if not impossible) to disentangle energy savings arising from the intervention and that arising from the Russian aggression in Ukraine and subsequent related energy crisis. Based on these calculations, participating Belgian households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of c. 1,747 kWh per household.

Table 2: Total Energy Consumption – Belgium (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final Data	Energy Savings	Primary Energy Savings
Electricity	1,760,512	1,637,276	123,236	234,148
Natural Gas	4,975,683	4,300,301	675,383	810,459
		Total	798,618	1,044,607

3 Bulgaria

3.1 Country overview – Bulgaria

3.1.1 Energy Poverty in Bulgaria

The term “energy poverty” remains undefined in Bulgarian legislation, with only the concept of “vulnerable consumers” is used. The Energy Act defines the term “vulnerable consumers” as “household customers in whose property, supplied with electricity, live persons who for reasons of old age, health or income are exposed to the risk of social exclusion about the supply and consumption of electricity and who benefit from social assistance measures to ensure the necessary electricity supplies”. Bulgaria is the poorest country in the EU (spending just 69% of the EU average⁵), and it perhaps no surprise that households tend to use cheap energy sources, such as wood and coal. Another country specific feature is that over 96% of housing is privately owned by individuals and over 85% of the useful living space is in buildings built before 2000, after which higher energy efficiency requirements came into force.

3.1.2 Energy sources in Bulgaria

The 2020 energy balance of the country shows that about 25% of the final energy is used in the households. Another cross-section of the statistical data shows the final energy consumption by different sources. The highest percentage (36%) is for the oil-based liquid fuels mainly used in the transport. Second place is for electricity (26%). The share of renewable energy sources is 16.3% which was the national goal up to 2020.

Figure 8: Energy consumption by sector, Bulgaria.

⁵ In terms of actual individual consumption (AIC) according to Eurostat data for 2022.
 February 2024

About 75% of the electricity in the country is generated by the few coal power plants (39%) and one nuclear power plant in Kozloduy (37%). Coal is mainly mined locally while nuclear fuel, formerly supplied from Russia (before the invasion of Ukraine), now comes from France and the US⁶.

Figure 9: Energy consumption by source, Bulgaria.

Currently, there are no detailed statistics on the distribution of different energy sources in household consumption, but according to the National Long-Term Renovation Strategy (Bulgarian Government 2017) about 36% of the energy in the household sector is provided by solid fuels (mostly firewood and coal), characterised by extremely low cost and having a strong negative impact on air pollution. Such fuels are mostly used in rural areas and small towns. Energy from district heating accounts for 18% and electricity (including heating) for 45%. It is the latter two that are the most used sources for heating in urban environments. The use of natural gas for domestic heating is still insignificant as a share.

The available data on the energy performance of multi-family residential buildings, presented in the National Long-Term Renovation Strategy, show that buildings with energy classes between E and G have the highest share, which is actually logical given the lack of financial instruments and communication with households about the benefits of energy efficiency, which in any case should not be considered only from a financial point of view, as high CO₂ levels, the presence of mould and condensation and high dust levels lead to increased health issues for the population.

3.1.3 Bulgarian energy-related challenges

Having lived in poverty for many years, most Bulgarian households have long ago, and the hard way, arrived at a large set of behavioural measures leading to energy reduction and increased comfort (sticking sealing strips on windows in winter, turning off or reducing heating in unoccupied rooms, using a night tariff for electric water heaters, etc.). However, this is always done at a household level, and in fact the sustainable solution to energy poverty is deep renovation. Unfortunately, this is where the main problem lies, and that is the association of owners of multi-family residential buildings to introduce large-scale energy efficiency

⁶ <https://world-nuclear-news.org/Articles/Kozloduy-and-Framatome-sign-nuclear-fuel-agreement>
 February 2024

measures at the building level. The most recent evidence of this problem was the extremely low interest in participating in the National Programme for Energy Efficiency, where despite the 100% grant offered on the sole condition that individual owners create an association, gathering 2000 buildings to participate in the programme proved to be a challenge.

3.2 Participating households – Bulgaria

3.2.1 Background

Local authorities played the key role in attracting households to participate in the programme, and those that put effort into organising meetings with households and awareness campaigns also achieved the best results. Burgas and Gabrovo municipalities who are members of the Municipal Energy Efficiency Network - EcoEnergy⁷, committed to support the organisation of meetings with household representatives in multi-family residential buildings. A major factor that weighed in the selection of households to participate in the project was the migration of the population from the villages to the cities, where housing is mainly in multi-family apartment buildings built during the socialist era. In recent years there has also been a reverse migration, but mostly from more affluent households to the villages around the large cities. Therefore, EcoEnergy's focus during the EnergyMeasures project was on the occupants of older multi-family residential buildings where a larger share of the population in Bulgaria lives. A total of 723 households were recruited in nine multifamily residential buildings in Gabrovo and Burgas. Energy audits were provided for these buildings and the resident householders, where energy consumption in the buildings were analysed in detail and specific recommendations for the implementation of energy efficiency measures made.

3.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

Households participating in the programme in Bulgaria are living in multifamily residential building commissioned between 1960 and 1980 during the Soviet era. Almost equally distributed to 1, 2, 3 and 4 persons per household all of them are living in 2 or 3 room apartments. About 75 of the dwellings are not insulated, 25% installed with 5 cm of EPS on the external walls and few have thicker insulation up to 10 cm. The windows are usually double glazed without selective coating and the framework is either old wooden examples or in some cases replaced PVC.

3.3 Energy consumption data – Bulgaria

The buildings in Bulgaria were nine multifamily residential buildings comprising large numbers of housing units. The nature of these building poses specific challenges in reducing energy consumption (*e.g.*, often limited local controls on older district heating systems) and in improving the energy performance of the building due to the condominium ownership arrangements. The EnergyMeasures engagement with the residents led to collaboration with homeowner associations (HOA) to develop the householder cooperation required to progress the building renovation programmes. This explains why the estimated energy savings

⁷ Burgas and Gabrovo municipalities were so-called linked third parties of EcoEnergy within this project.

are quite elevated compared to the other partners – as the savings are based on the modelled performance of the building once planned renovation is realised.

Table 3: Participating households - Bulgaria

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Electricity	578	8
District Heating	128	104
Biomass	8	26
Total # households	723	Average # residents
		1.83

The baseline data shown in the table below was calculated based on actual energy data of the participating households within the nine multifamily residential buildings. EcoEnergy, together with representatives of the municipalities of Burgas and Gabrovo, engaged with relevant suppliers on behalf of the participating households to get relevant data direct from suppliers. This proved quite successful and as a result, monthly data for a three-year period in relation to electricity consumption, heat consumption, and water use was obtained from electricity distribution companies, district heating companies and water utilities respectively. A consumption correction was applied – as provided for in Bulgarian national legislation – for the performance of detailed energy audits of buildings. The final energy consumption data (and by extension the forecast ‘energy savings’) were calculated through energy audits based on the measures to be undertaken during planned renovation⁸. Based on these calculations, participating Bulgarian households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of c. 9,789 kWh per household.

Table 4: Total Energy Consumption – Bulgaria (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final Data	Energy Savings	Primary Energy Savings
Electricity	7,536,682	5,199,280	2,337,402	4,441,063
District heating ⁹	3,619,624	1,287,261	2,332,363	2,565,599
Biomass	473,257	120,382	352,875	70,575
		Total	5,022,640	7,077,238

⁸ The calculated ‘energy saving’ will be confirmed through energy bills following implementation of the energy efficiency measures.

⁹ District heating converted to primary energy using BG national coefficient 1.3 (Latöšov *et al.*, 2013).

4 Ireland

4.1 Country overview – Ireland

4.1.1 Energy Poverty in Ireland

Ireland’s Energy Poverty Strategy estimates that the rate of households experiencing energy poverty in the country falls between 8.8 – 28%, depending on whether this is based on self-reported inability to heat or derived from modelled expenditure and building energy rating data (DCENR, 2016). In 2016, this upper estimate would have been equivalent to 475,000 households. More recent research produced by the Economic and Social Research Institute (ESRI) in 2020 revises this figure, estimating ‘core’ energy poverty to be 17.5% of households throughout Ireland, approximately 297,000 in total (O’Malley *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, the Survey on Income and Living Conditions (SILC) indicates that the proportion of those who self-report being unable to afford to heat their homes has fallen from 9% in 2015 to 4.9% in 2019 (Lawlor & Visser, 2022). As can be deduced from these variable estimates, it is relatively difficult to discern a true picture of the levels of energy poverty throughout Ireland.

4.1.2 Energy sources in Ireland

Ireland’s economy is strongly reliant on fossil fuels, with 86% of all energy used in the country stemming from fossil fuel-based sources in 2010. The residential sector is the second-largest source of energy demand in the country, behind the transport sector, as of 2020 (SEAI, undated).

Figure 10: Percentage (%) share of primary energy by fuel for 2020 (SEAI, undated).

Primary energy fell by 8.7% in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Oil remains the dominant energy source, and is mostly used for transport, followed by heating. Natural gas, the next largest source of energy, is mainly used for electricity generation. Within the share of renewable energy, 56% of this is accounted for by wind energy (SEAI, undated).

Figure 11: Final energy use by mode in 2020 (SEAI, undated).

As shown in Figure 11, heat became the largest mode of energy use in 2020 at c. 44% of the total; this was followed by transport (34%) and electricity (22%).

4.1.3 Irish energy-related challenges

Ireland is currently in the process of attempting to transition to a low-carbon energy system, which presents several unique challenges for the country, namely energy security, meeting climate commitments, energy costs, sectoral issues and challenges around physical infrastructure development and employment opportunities:

In terms of energy security, Ireland has a heavy reliance on external sources of energy, being identified as the 10th most dependent EU Member State in 2016. Energy imports cost Ireland €5.0 billion in 2018. International developments like the war in Ukraine and Brexit are likely to have an impact on Ireland's energy security in future (Byrne Ó Cléirigh, 2020). As of 2014, Ireland was halfway to meeting its climate change targets across all sectors and the overall target for 2020. Ireland was recently called out for being off track in meeting its interim GHG emissions targets for both 2020 and 2030, for decarbonising the Irish economy by 2050. Based on projections, Ireland was expected to exceed its EU Effort Sharing Decision target of 338m t CO₂e by c. 16m t.

The cost of energy supply is significant from the perspective of a country's competitiveness and growth potential; it is also a key resource for businesses and an important item in the household budget for consumers. For low-income households, the cost of energy can prove to be a particular challenge. At the time of writing in early 2022, electricity prices in Ireland were 26% above the EU average, coming in behind only Germany, Belgium and Denmark (Eurostat). Ireland was identified as the eight most expensive country in the EU for gas. Compared to the EU average, however, energy is one of the few areas where Irish citizens are taxed relatively lightly. However, the Carbon Tax as part of Budget 2021 included an increase of €7.50 from the previous €26 per tonne to €33.50 per tonne for auto fuels from October 2020 and solid fuels from May 2021; this will continue up to 2030 (Ireland's EU emissions target). The price increases have had an effect on gas and diesel, as well as electric power stations driven by gas, and will impact the Irish public; the

government has subsequently introduced €200 refund credits to all householders on their recent fuel bills which will be drawn down from the Carbon Tax Funds (Eurostat).

Certain sectors can present unique circumstances in relation to energy and its use. The transportation sector, for example, is heavily reliant on fossil fuels and a major rethink would be required to prevent increases in greenhouse gas emissions from this sector. Other sectors, like the technology sector, may present specific challenges arising from energy-intensive activities, like the operation of data centres; in 2021, a total of 14% of the total electricity requirement demand came from data centres (CSO 2022).

Currently, Ireland lacks the necessary physical infrastructure, like energy networks and interconnection with other countries' energy systems, that will be required to make the transition to decarbonise the energy system. At present, Ireland is focusing on becoming a major investment hub for Clean Technology, driven by energy price hikes, environmental issues, and resource shortages; the country offers abundant natural resources, a strong research and development environment, high-level skills and supportive policies at government level which continue to support its success in this pursuit.

4.2 Participating households – Ireland

4.2.1 Background

In Ireland, the project focused its activities on two areas. In Dublin and environs, the primary target group were urban dwelling elderly people living in single-family, owner-occupied houses. In the Cork area, the engagements concentrated primarily on disadvantaged communities in Cork city and surrounding satellite towns along with several one-off rural housing units. In Dublin, it was originally envisaged that local authorities would play a significant role in the recruitment of households. However, Covid-19, had a significant impact on accessing homes and accessing key local authority staff, and the strategy was changed to liaising with private households directly and through gatekeeper organisations. Recruitment activities included the distribution of leaflets with information about the project and energy advice at key locations such as senior citizen complexes and through gatekeepers such as: Money and Budgetary Service, Saint Vincent de Paul Society, Senior Citizen Groups, Friends of the Elderly, Age Action, Third Age Ireland, ALONE, etc. In Cork, recruitment activities included distribution of leaflets in target areas, working through with local organisations and holding energy clinics in community centres and through active retirement associations.

4.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

The participating households in Ireland were recruited principally from Dublin City and Cork City areas. Most of the Irish participating households were owner-occupied, with a smaller proportion of social housing (both local authorities and housing associations). This is reflective of the target groups selected for Ireland and especially of the gatekeeper organisations employed to assist in recruitment. Most dwellings were two story houses with between 6 and 11 rooms in total. The participating dwellings were predominately semi-detached (suburban areas especially), mid-terrace (city centres) or detached house (peri-urban), with apartments account for only a small proportion. Typically, these houses were constructed in either of two periods: mid-1800s or between 1930 and 2000. The level of energy efficiency in the homes was poor, with around one in ten having little if any insulation, and a not insignificant number having single-glazed windows.

Figure 12: House in Cork City

Figure 13: Apartment building in Dublin City

Figure 14: House in Dublin City

The main challenges experienced by households participating in the project were mould and dampness (Figure 15) in rooms, in addition to draughts from older and/or poorly maintained windows (many with wooden frames).

Another issue was the prevalence of pre-payment meters, a scheme usually offered to bill payers with poor credit. However, this is worrying since the cost per unit through such meters can often be higher depending on supplier¹⁰ In addition, a high percentage of households have never switched suppliers. As a result, there

¹⁰ The cost of energy through prepaid meters has historically been higher than if paid for by other means (Hills, 2011).
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was an emphasis placed on increasing the energy literacy of householders and helping them to switch suppliers.

Figure 15: Examples of mould and dampness in dwellings (Cork City)

Figure 16: Examples of wooden and aluminium windows in dwellings (Cork City)

4.3 Energy consumption data– Ireland

Table 5: Participating households - Ireland

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Heating oil	283	50
Natural gas	194	60
Solid fuel	89	51
Electricity	34	60
Other	2	3

Total # households	603	Average # residents	2.45
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Baseline data on energy consumption was collected from participating households during initial registration and engagement. This involved the available collection of available electricity and where relevant natural gas bills. As appropriate energy advisers assisted householders in sourcing and understanding their energy bills. Information on other energy supplies such as heating oil and solid fuels (coal, peat, etc.) was also collected at this time, given the *ad hoc* purchases of such fuels, this data was based on householder estimations, expressed in terms of cost and/or quantity and converted to kWh. This data collection exercise was repeated towards the end of the project. In addition, we were able to source aggregated monthly consumption data (for 2021-24) from a major electricity supplier for their participating customers (representing c. one-fifth of all participants) This month-by-month anonymised aggregated dataset combined with the information sourced directly from participants provided good insight into energy consumption trends. Using this combined information, hypothetical full year ‘baseline’ and ‘final’ energy consumption was calculated as summarised in Table 6 below. During the period of the project, it is calculated that participating Irish households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of 1,423kWh per household.

Table 6: Total Energy Consumption – Ireland (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final data	Energy savings	Primary energy savings
Electricity	2,013,272	1,847,779	165,493	314,437
Heating oil	6,508,258	6,352,060	156,198	171,818
Natural gas	2,073,639	1,742,261	331,378	397,654
Solid fuel	2,727,901	2,751,449	-23,548	-25,903 ¹¹
		Total	629,521	858,006

¹¹ The negative number for solid fuel indicates an increase in consumption, implying a partial shift from electricity and gas to *ad hoc* purchases of solids fuels during the recent energy crisis.

5 The Netherlands

5.1 Country overview – Netherlands

5.1.1 Energy poverty in the Netherlands

In the Netherlands, approximately 550,000 households live in energy poverty (out of a total of 8 million households). They spend more than 10% of their disposable income per month on paying the energy bill or have too little left after paying the necessary expenses to get by. For Eindhoven, it is calculated that approximately 14,000 (out of a total of 122,000) households live in energy poverty. This number puts Eindhoven in fifth place nationwide, with only other big cities such as Amsterdam and Rotterdam with higher numbers of energy poverty. In Eindhoven, approximately 11,500 households are counted as having minimal means. The problem with energy poverty thus goes beyond the households that are known and already receive a form of (financial) support from the municipality (Mulder *et al.* 2021).

Figure 17: Distribution of energy poverty by municipality (left) and district (right) (Mulder *et al.* 2021 p.7)

Figure 18: Energy poverty distribution in Eindhoven (derived from TNO (undated) interactive energy poverty map)

5.1.2 Energy sources in the Netherlands

The Netherlands mainly uses natural gas and oil. Only a small part of the energy used comes from other sources such as coal, nuclear energy or sustainably generated energy. In the 1950s, the largest natural gas field in the world was discovered in the north of the country, in the province of Groningen. This led to an extensive network of natural gas pipelines throughout the country. Natural gas also became an important export product for the Netherlands. Private households still use natural gas almost exclusively to heat their houses, 95% of Dutch houses Netherlands are connected to the gas network.

The problem with natural gas in the Netherlands is that its extraction causes earthquakes that cause considerable damage to homes and buildings in the province. That is why the Dutch government has decided to phase out the extraction of natural gas. Less natural gas may be extracted every year and the plan is to completely stop extracting natural gas by 2030. The problem, however, is that the Netherlands is now buying additional natural gas from other countries, especially from Russia. In view of the geopolitical situation, this is not desirable and there is talk of increasing the quota for gas extraction in Groningen after all.

Petroleum is extracted in three places in the Netherlands. However, most of the petroleum used in the Netherlands is imported via the port of Rotterdam. This oil comes mainly from Russia, Norway, Saudi Arabia, and some other small oil-producing countries. The oil goes to oil refineries and is mainly used in industry. Private households do nothing with petroleum.

It goes without saying that the Netherlands is also taking steps towards generating sustainable energy. The focus is on wind and solar energy and energy generated during the processing of biomass. In time, in 2050, the Netherlands will say goodbye to natural gas and all energy used will come from renewable sources. In 2021 12.5% of the total energy consumption was generated sustainably

Figure 19: Energy by source, Netherlands (Adapted from EBN B.V. 2022)

5.1.3 Major energy related challenges

As described above, the extraction of natural gas in the Netherlands has led to earthquakes in the extraction area. To prevent this issue, for the last number of years less gas has been extracted and gas has been imported. The plan is to phase out the extraction of natural gas step-by-step, partly to be less dependent on imported gas. In time, it is planned that the Netherlands will generate all the necessary energy itself via renewable sources. Natural gas is mainly imported from Russia. However, the war in Ukraine has changed the situation and the Netherlands no longer wants (and may not be able) to import natural gas from Russia. However, the Netherlands is highly dependent on natural gas. Major problems and further price increases are expected for the autumn of 2022 and beyond. After all, we are not sure of supplying enough gas and the costs will be enormous.

At present, 12.5% of the energy used in the Netherlands is sustainably generated. The targets are for this to be 49% in 2030 and 100% in 2050. To achieve this, major adjustments are needed to the energy infrastructure. For example, all homes in the Netherlands must be disconnected from natural gas by 2050. These adjustments cost a lot of time and money. In addition, support for this energy transition is not equally high among all Dutch people. The war in Ukraine and rising energy bills created a new kind of energy consciousness.

5.2 Participating households – Netherlands

5.2.1 Background

The Municipality of Eindhoven, supported by DuneWorks & het PON & Telos, led household engagement in the Netherlands where they had a recruitment target of 400 households. The municipality initiated various parallel recruitment processes to increase the odds of recruiting enough households – who met the criteria, these largely consisted of social tenants but also included some private resident). The EnergyMeasures project was connected to existing projects and processes as much as possible. In particular, the Municipality of Eindhoven works closely with Energiebox, an NGO that allows energy coaches to visit households for a one-off conversation about energy consumption and provide some small energy savings products. While this initiative is available to all households and is not as intensive an engagement as that envisaged in EnergyMeasures, it is complementary to the work of the project, and proved a source of referrals. The history and recognition factor of this initiative was leveraged by positioning the EnergyMeasures project in Eindhoven as 'Energiebox Plus'. The Eindhoven tailored approach was that trained energy coaches enter into a trajectory for a year with a household that was dealing with energy poverty. They kept in touch with them on a regular basis and supported them with advice and where appropriate with referrals to other supports. The aim was for the household to regain control of its energy bill after a year of assistance, to have more insight into how energy can be saved and, as required, to be referred to the right social institution. In this way the project contributed to the resilience of vulnerable households.

5.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

The households in Eindhoven that have a higher chance of experiencing energy poverty, more often rent through a housing association, more often live in a house built before 1969 (with an energy label of lower than D) and are most often in the lowest income groups. A higher preponderance of energy poverty is also observed amongst households comprising single people or single-parent families. The figures below shows an example of social housing outlining the street layout and exterior structure of the homes, typical of the households recruited in Eindhoven.

Figure 20: Example #1 of social housing (layout & structure) in Eindhoven

The dwellings recruited in these are share a number of characteristics include, e.g., single pane glass windows, lack of ventilation in bathrooms, non-insulated brick walls, old wooden door and window frames, most of the times with wood rot causing draughts in the house (see figures below).

Figure 21: Example of draughty door & window fittings

Figure 22: Example of window used for bathroom venting

5.3 Energy consumption data – Netherlands

Table 7: Participating households - Netherlands

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Natural Gas	403	
Total # households	403	Average # residents
		2.35 ¹²

Natural gas has a very high adoption rate in the Netherlands, it is estimated that 4 in 5 Dutch homes have gas heating and that some 73% of total final consumption is accounted for by natural gas. All of the participating household in the Netherlands had natural gas as their primary heat source. The focus of the engagement in the Netherlands was in Eindhoven, where the municipality led engagement supported by two other local partners).

Energy consumption data (i.e., electricity and gas bills) were collected from householders by energy advisers when they made their initial visit, and again towards the end of the project during a follow up call & visit. While there are often many understandable reasons why households could not supply such information¹³, consumption data was collected for 366 households (91%), which offers a good insight into trends over the duration. Baseline and final data both electricity and gas are presented in Table 8 below, along with calculations of delivered energy savings and primary energy savings.

The nature of residential heating provision in the Netherlands makes it is possible to clearly between heating and non-heating energy consumption. During the period of the project, electricity energy consumption is down by 10.5% compared to 11.9% for thermal energy heating in the same period. During this time, it is calculated that participating Dutch households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of 1,732 kWh per household.

Table 8: Total Energy Consumption – Netherlands (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final data	Energy savings	Primary energy savings
Electricity	793,488	711,874	81,614	155,066
Natural gas	3,798,920	3,346,644	452,276	542,731
		Total	533,890	697,798

¹² Estimated

¹³ (i) Some households do not have access to the internet and so did not have access to their data through online accounts. (ii) Households' debt restructuring, have their debts, but also their income taken over by a financial specialist – such householders have no idea about their consumption data. (iii) Many people are distrustful of care providers or the municipality – talking about finances or consumption data would have hindered the trust building. (iv) Many people struggle to get through the day, and they have little feeling for their financial administration. (iv) Sometimes people move often and lose track of their administration or energy costs.

6 North Macedonia

6.1 Country Overview – North Macedonia

6.1.1 Energy poverty in North Macedonia

The combination of high poverty and unemployment rates; outdated and inefficient heating systems; low energy performance of buildings and appliances; and (relatively) high energy prices means that energy poverty is widespread among North Macedonian households. Energy expenditures take a (increasingly) high share of already low-income levels. It is estimated that 35% of Macedonian households had difficulties in paying their energy bills, while nearly one-quarter of households reported being unable to keep their home adequately warm, one of the highest in Europe as shown in Figure 23 below (Farrugia 2022). Stojilovska *et al.* (2021) observe that the country has ‘a weak social protection system with a low net social welfare and strict criteria for social welfare participants’.

Figure 23: Proportion of the population unable to adequately warm (Eurostat data cited in Farrugia 2022)

For those heating their homes with electricity the most pressing problem is the disconnection from the grid – while others suffer from indoor and outdoor air pollution associated with burning solid fuels. Too often, households under-consume energy by reducing heating below comfort levels.

6.1.2 Energy Sources in North Macedonia

According to the Government of North Macedonia 36.5 percent of the energy is used by households, the industrial sector uses 26.6 percent of energy, and the rest is used by other sectors. In North Macedonia the main sources of energy are gas, fuel oil, electrical energy, and wood pellets. However, natural gas is not available for the Macedonian residential sector. Six out of ten households consume fuelwood as the primary energy source for heating (State Statistical Office 2015), with the country’s forests and woods representing an affordable heating source for many. In North Macedonia, the Austrian owned electricity supply company has a monopoly position. Approximately 70% of electricity is sourced from hydropower plants from artificial lakes with the rest is imported from other parts of Europe. A further c. 30% of households use electricity for heating in addition to their other needs.

6.1.3 Major Energy-Related Challenges

The reliance on wood for such a large proportion of heating requirements means that North Macedonia's forest ecosystems are heavily degraded, while Macedonian cities are known to be among the most polluted in Europe. Skopje for example has one of the highest PM₁₀ concentrations according to the WHO list of 2600 European cities. In parallel, the annual CO₂ during 2000s reached 5.5 tonnes per capita, close to per capita levels of some industrially developed EU countries and higher than all other SEE countries. While the state has a small energy subsidy to combat energy poverty it is not substantial, and the threat of disconnection for the electricity grid is a real worry for many.

6.2 Participating households – North Macedonia

6.2.1 Background

Energy is used inefficiently in North Macedonia, with per capita consumption intensity significantly above the average for the European Union. The high energy intensity is a result of aged and often obsolete energy infrastructure and poorly maintained and/or outdated energy-using capital stock – especially in buildings. Residential multi-apartment buildings, estimated at about 11,500 in North Macedonia, account for a significant share of the total energy consumption in buildings and are at the same time highly energy inefficient. According to findings of the Western Balkans Residential Energy Efficiency Market Assessment, the penetration rates of energy efficient materials, appliances and equipment is very low in North Macedonia (on average not exceeding 10%), especially in households with lower incomes.

6.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

The majority of the buildings in North Macedonia are 30 to 50 years old, lack thermal insulation and have poor energy performance. About 6% of all residential building stock in Macedonia is estimated to meet the national energy performance requirements and belong to energy class C or D, while all other residential buildings can be classified in lower energy classes thus need energy efficiency retrofitting. Habidom manages 146 multifamily residential apartment buildings located on the territory of Skopje each with 20-30 households. The participating households were recruited from amongst this pool. As building managers, Habidom had good communications channels with these households.

Figure 24: One of the multifamily residential building in Skopje managed by Habidom

6.3 Energy consumption data – North Macedonia

Table 9: Participating households – North Macedonia

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Electricity	377	
District heating	243	
Total # households	620	Average # residents
		3.1

Over 60% of the participating households in North Macedonia used electricity to heat their homes, with the remaining homes collected to district heating systems. The district heating systems are quite antiquated and there is little if any local control. Additionally, as all households receive the same ‘heat service’ for a set fee there is no incentive to reduce consumption – even if there was a way of doing so at the household level. For that reason, the energy conservation and efficiency measures adopted focused on electricity, and accordingly the monitoring focused on electricity consumption.

Each of the participating households reside in a building managed by Residential building management company Habidom DOOEL Skopje. As the building management company, Habidom has good communication links with the participating households and direct access to the buildings in which they are located. Utility bills were collected from the households during the initial visits once the householder eligibility had been confirmed and they had agreed to participate in the project. This allowed a baseline of annualised electricity consumption to be calculated as shown in Table 10 below. Then over the life of the project, electricity bills for to the householders were collected and analysed to monitor trends in consumption and to determine an annualised electricity consumption at the end of the project as outlined below.

During the period of the project, it is calculated that participating North Macedonian households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of 920 kWh per household. This is the lowest reductions in energy consumption seen across the seven countries (equating with 9% reduction in consumption). This reflects the fact that the heating of 40% of participating households (*i.e.*, where service was provided by district heating systems) were largely dis-incentivised from reducing their energy consumption given the antiquated arrangements that remain in place¹⁴.

Table 10: Total Energy Consumption – North Macedonia (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final Data	Energy Savings	Primary Energy Savings
Electricity	3,373,541	3,073,432	300,109	570,207
		Total	300,109	570,207

¹⁴ This district heating service is charged at a flat rate per square meter
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7 Poland

7.1 Country overview – Poland

7.1.1 Energy Poverty in Poland

Energy poverty is a significant problem in Poland. Before the pandemic, it affected 12% of Poland's inhabitants. In 2020, this number increased to 21.4% – aggravated by job losses and falling wages, especially among people with low and middle incomes. In Poland, the share of expenditure on electricity, gas and other fuels as a proportion of total household expenditure is twice as high as the EU average. The vast majority of people experiencing energy poverty live in single-family houses. In 2016, it was 75.4% of all energy poor, *i.e.*, 3.47 million people. This problem largely affects people living in rural areas and elderly people living alone. Energy poverty mainly affects the inhabitants of houses built in the years 1946–1960 (51%). The reason may be the low energy efficiency of these buildings, *e.g.*, lack of thermal insulation or draughty windows. There are regional differences in the manifestation of the issue. The problem of too high energy costs compared to available income is especially visible in Eastern Poland, while the problem of under heated households is to the fore in western regions of the country

Figure 25: House built before 90s without thermomodernisation (Source: czysteogrzewanie.pl)

7.1.2 Energy Sources in Poland

The main energy source in Poland is coal. In 2020, coal was responsible for almost 70% of electricity generation (Anthracite or 'hard coal' at 44.1% and Lignite at 24.1 %). However, by 2023, coal was reduced to an all-time low of 61% of electricity generation, with renewable energy increasing substantially to 27%, more than doubling since 2014. The most important carriers in the renewable group were wind energy, biomass and biogas. Solar energy had the smallest share, but it was characterised by the highest growth dynamics. There was a 10 TWh reduction in Polish domestic power generation during 2023. This was due to a 3% or 5

TWh demand reduction, and the replacement of the previous year's 2 TWh of exports with 3 TWh of imports in 2023 (Czyżak 2024).

Figure 26: Share of energy sources in Poland (Source: ARE)

Households' energy consumption accounts for approx. 25% of the total final energy consumption in the country. The most important direction of energy use in the household sector is space heating, the share of which amounts to about 63%. Approximately 17% of energy is used for heating water, 11% for lighting and household appliances, and 9% for cooking meals.

According to the latest study by the Central Statistical Office on energy consumption in households, the most frequently used are solid fuels, mainly hard coal and fuel wood. These fuels are mostly used for space heating (45.4% of households). They were used also for water heating (25.6%), and much less for cooking (3.2%). District heat was used in 40.4% of all dwellings, mainly in cities where it was the predominating commodity (58.3%). Moreover 31.5% of households, *i.e.*, 78.2% of all district heating consumers, obtained heated water from the district installation. Natural gas was used in 55.7% of households, but more than half of consumers (51.9%) used it only for cooking, and only 14.0% for space heating. Such a consumption structure was the outcome of a long-lasting practice of installing gas networks in multi-family buildings only for cooking purposes. In those areas of the country which have no access to natural gas, the stationary use of LPG was more common (34.0%), though it was almost exclusively used for cooking (33.9%). Fuel wood was used by 29.9% of households. It was the only renewable energy commodity used by households on a large scale. It was usually burnt in the same boilers and stoves as hard coal, either together with coal or interchangeably. Apart from fuel wood, households also used other types of biomass, though they were far less common than wood. Solar collectors were used by one out of 52 households, and heat pumps by as few as one out of 200. Electricity was commonly used by households, mainly for lighting as well as electrical appliances and electronic devices. The use of electricity for heating purposes was insignificant (5.1%), due to high prices and the availability of cheaper substitutes. Electricity was used for cooking and space heating, usually on a secondary basis, whereas its use for water heating was common mainly in those areas which did not have access to the heating or gas network.

7.2 Participating households – Poland

7.2.1 Background

The target for household recruitment Poland was to engage 400 households. The focal area was Bielsko-Biała, a city in southern Poland, with a population of approximately 166,765. The EnergyMeasures project was implemented in Bielsko-Biała, in cooperation with city authorities. The city decided to join the project as it cares both for its citizens and for the environment and the climate. Climate mitigation & adaptation actions undertaken by local administration are coherent with the sustainable development rules, which state that strive for the economic well-being of inhabitants needs to take place in harmony with nature, considering the needs of future generations and without leaving anyone behind. The responsibility for project activities was granted to the Environmental Protection and Energy Department. The primary focus of the project was on the two-target groups: Private owners occupying single-family buildings (with the focus on the elderly and the families leaving on social benefits), and Private owners of flats in multi-family buildings (again, with the focus on the elderly and the families leaving on social benefits)

7.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

The situation in Bielsko-Biała looks a bit different from the national picture, as the city started to work on energy efficiency already in the 90s. That caused a decrease in the consumption of coal. It is related, inter alia, with a change in the method of heating new facilities to gas, district heat and electricity, as well as to the application of high standards of energy efficiency of newly constructed facilities. The housing stock is characterised by unfavourable age and technological structure - buildings built until 1945 dominate constituting over 73% of the total number of buildings.

Figure 27: Location Bielsko-Biała in Poland.

Figure 28: Different types of buildings in Bielsko-Biala.

This age profile implies substantial renovation and modernization needs, (and not unrelatedly) significant maintenance costs. The municipality manages around 1,400 buildings across the city, of which only about 6% were built after 1970. The historic substance of Bielsko-Biala is primarily the Old Town and dispersed historic objects. Currently, the designated contractual boundaries of the Old Town cover the area of about 10 ha. The physical state of many buildings in that part of the city is very bad and they require major repairs.

Nearly half of households have an LPG boiler as the main heating source and one-third has a connection to a district heating network. Other sources aren't really popular in the households engaged. The large number using gas sources (the heating network also needs gas) may cause difficulties with payments for citizens in the close future, as the gas resources, supplies and especially prices are related to the situation in Ukraine. Among the participating households, there are substantial amount which use additional heating source. The most popular option is to have a stove, which can be used occasionally. Some people use electric heaters (especially plug-in heaters). Free-standing cast iron stoves and even ovens were mentioned as others.

7.3 Energy consumption data – Poland

Table 11: Participating households – Poland

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Natural Gas	210	9
District Heating	175	0
Solid fuel	58	80
Electricity	7	40
Heating oil	0	5

Total # households	450	Average # residents	2.24
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Baseline data on energy consumption was collected from participating households during the initial engagement. Where available invoices were collected, and the quantity of energy consumed (kWh) recorded for the year 2021. When invoices weren't available, source of energy was different (e.g., coal, oil) or residents were unable to read the data, participants were encouraged to share information about the amount expended on energy (PLN, zł), subsequently converted to kWh. Participants committed to supplying energy data. An online form for data collection was designed and disseminated through a variety of channels. Towards the end of the project PNEC initiated direct contact with through phone calls. Through these processes data as collected from 176 householders (c. 40% of participants), which enabled findings to be statistically extrapolated to the full group¹⁵. Using this information, annualised 'baseline' and 'final' energy consumption was calculated as summarised in Table 12 below. During the period of the project, it is calculated that participating Polish households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of 9,497kWh per household. This is the second highest reduction in consumption across the seven focal countries.

Table 12: Total Energy Consumption – Poland (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final Data	Energy Savings	Primary Energy Savings
Electricity	1,341,975	1,111,555	230,419	437,797
Natural gas	5,539,821	3,087,049	2,452,772	2,943,327
Coal ¹⁶	1,661,125	909,972	751,153	826,268
Biomass ¹⁶	499,635	168,239	331,396	66,279
		Total	3,765,740	4,273,671

¹⁵ With a 6% margin of error

¹⁶ We note a focus on primary heat sources in the data collection, which adds additional uncertainty regarding secondary use of coal and wood.

8 United Kingdom (Scotland)

8.1 Country Overview – Scotland, UK

8.1.1 Energy poverty in Scotland

The Scottish House condition survey Key Findings 2018 report (2020) showed the fluctuation of energy (fuel) poverty levels in Scotland, as can be seen below.

Figure 29: Scottish house condition survey: 2018 key findings (Scottish Government, 2020)

The numbers for 2019 came in slightly lower overall, at an estimated 24.6%. Extreme fuel poverty increased to 12.4%. However, the more important development for remote rural (and island) Scotland saw fuel poverty levels increase from 33% (already significantly higher than cities and large towns) to 43%, with extreme fuel poverty rising from 23% to 33%. There are no Western Isles¹⁷ only figures available as no survey is done islands wide each year.

Post 2019, data collection methods changed to reflect ‘The Fuel Poverty (Targets, Definition and Strategy) (Scotland) Act 2019’. This Act established the following fuel poverty targets for 2040:

- no more than 5% of households in Scotland are in fuel poverty.
- no more than 1% of households in Scotland are in extreme fuel poverty.
- the median fuel poverty gap of households in Scotland in fuel poverty is no more than GBP £250 adjusted to take account of changes in the value of money.

However, due to the nature of the Scottish House Condition Survey, *i.e.*, door to door review of house types and households, because of Covid it was deemed impossible to conduct such an exercise.

¹⁷ The Western Isles (Scots Gaelic: Na h-Eileanan Siar) also known as The Outer Hebrides is an island chain off the west coast of mainland Scotland

8.1.2 Energy sources in Scotland

Energy efficiency, the impact of the economic cycles, prevalent energy price cost increases and weather patterns have all played a role in reducing overall energy consumption by over 24,000 GWh from 2005 to 2020. Provisional figures for 2020 show Scotland’s final energy consumption was 14.4% below the 2005-07 baseline, a record low, and represents a 0.1% decrease in total energy consumption between 2019 and 2020. Scotland has met its energy consumption target (Scottish Government, undated). Energy consumption in the domestic sector is 44.2 TWh. This is a decrease of 16.1% from 2005-07, which may reflect improvements in energy efficiency in the domestic building stock in this time (Scottish Government, undated).

Figure 30: Scottish Energy consumption 2020 compared to 2005/07

Figure 31: Total Installed capacity renewable electricity in Scotland (data from UK National Archives 2011; UK Government 2022)

Figure 32: Current installed renewable capacity, Scotland (Source: BEIS Energy Trends)

This chart is to show how much onshore wind generation has expanded in Scotland. This is particularly so in remote rural areas, which despite large areas of community owned wind generation, still suffers highest levels of fuel poverty in Scotland, indeed has the highest unit rate for electricity (due to transmission costs of returning energy from the grid). This will be picked on in the next section, as the project works in such an area of high generation with highest levels of fuel poverty.

8.2 Participating households – Scotland, UK

8.2.1 Background

As one can see from the figure below energy efficiency at a national level in Scotland is improving, but nonetheless is mostly stagnant at an inefficient majority. The Energy Efficient Scotland: Routemap (Scottish Government 2018) sets an ambition for 'every Scottish home to achieve at least a band C in its Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) by 2040 (where technically feasible and cost effective). Linking into the Fuel Poverty Strategy (Scottish Government 2021), where this suggests fuel poverty is suffered by female households, 'more likely to be a female headed household' (51% vs 35%) this is why in the Outer Hebrides we chose to focus on women led households, where efficiency in homes is worse than Scotland as a whole, with more than 80% below EPC band C. The Scottish government are likely to propose legislation to phase out installation of new or replacement fossil fuel boilers not on mains gas from 2025 and those on mains gas from 2030 (Maby & Sunderland, 2022). Warmer Homes Scotland (delivery agency for energy efficiency measures Scotland wide) have already been stopped from installing replacement oil boilers with government funding.

Figure 33: Housing Stock Distribution by EPC Band, Scotland 2018-19 (Scottish Government)

Space heating in Scotland is split (as a majority) between electricity and gas in the central belt (Glasgow through to Edinburgh, where the majority of Scots live) and electricity and oil in rural areas. House types in Scotland can be categorised into the following groups: detached; semi-detached; terraced; flat, maisonette or apartment. Primary heating is met through these common energy vectors, however as one moves from cities into rural areas is usually supplemented by a secondary heating source, almost always biomass or solid fuel (wood, coal, or peat).

8.2.2 Characterisation of the dwellings

Stornoway, the main town in the Western Isles has the largest number of post 1930 buildings in the Outer Hebrides, hence a large proportion of these 44% cavity construction homes will be built there. Although we have not turned down households in Stornoway from the project, our focus is on detached homes and subsequently most of our caseload is outwith the town. This means that more of our properties will be non-cavity and more likely to be stone, solid brick or poured concrete. Our project focus has been on detached properties, and these will be broken down into when built / wall type. Essentially the older built the less likely to be insulated, hence high numbers with low insulation but a reasonably high number with insulation that will have been built more recently.

Figure 34: Common house types in the Outer Hebrides

Detached old stone House, approx. 1825

Traditional 1920s stone croft house

Croft house Poured concrete, c. 1930s

Semi-detached 1950s brick cavity house

Detached block cavity house, c. 1960s

Detached timber frame bungalow, 1990s

Primary Heating Types: Storage heaters are the most common form of electrical heating systems in the islands. Most households who use this type had systems installed 15-25 years ago). It is controlled by input and output dials which we have found to be often faulty, missing or that the households themselves do not understand how to use them to get the best out of them. The next most common heating system is an oil boiler, which may be internal or external, such boilers are used to heat water which is circulated in radiators around the property. Many properties in the Western Isles have inefficient old boilers over 30 years old. Other common fuels used to heat radiators include LPG, biomass or solid fuels such as coal or peat. Solid fuels can also be burned in an open fire with back-boiler. Reflective panels as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** can be fitted to the back of the radiator to conserve heat.

Secondary heating systems are usually a multifuel stove or electric panel or resistance heater. Multifuel stoves are usually 3-5 kw in output and are used to heat the main living room. Older households who do not have a stove may use an open fire. Open fires are not usually used in bedrooms anymore, and we have installed chimney balloons in unused fireplaces to block them. The multifuel stove can burn wood, coal or peat and can have its efficiency boosted to heat other rooms with a stove fan placed on top and directed towards open doors to direct heat towards other rooms. Peat was once the main fuel used in homes across the Outer Hebrides. Peat cutting remains an important part of island life for many, who still gather with family & friends out in the peatlands for the labour-intensive cutting and gathering. The soft peat is cut into blocks in the springtime and left to dry out for 2 weeks and then lifted and stacked for winter. Panel or resistance heaters are the next largest form of secondary heating in the islands. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows an electric resistance heater which is fairly common, *i.e.*, directional with two heat settings, 400w or 800w. This one is used to heat a living room in a home without a radiator or working stove in it.

8.3 Energy consumption data – Scotland, UK

Table 13: Participating households – Scotland, UK

	Primary heat source	Supplementary heat source
Heating oil	261	0
Electricity	159	26
Natural Gas	58	0
Solid fuel	33	0

Total # households	511	Average # residents	1.92
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Housing in the Western Isles is predominately comprised of very dispersed one-off detached houses, many of which would be considered very remote by conventional standards. TIG developed a smart survey tool through which information was collected from householders during reiteration. While there is a very small gas network serving around 1,500 households in the Stornoway area on Lewis and Harris, most households are dependent on electricity and heating oil to heat their homes. During the first household visitation in-depth energy consumption data (for electricity and other energy) was collected from the householders. Where records were not readily available (e.g., because households have *ad hoc* energy purchases e.g., fuel oil, solid fuel), estimates were made using householders' recollections, and taking dwelling size into account. This allowed a baseline of energy consumption to be calculated as shown in Table 14 below. During the period of the project, it is calculated that participating Scottish households had a reduced annual primary energy consumption of 2,871 kWh per household – the highest reduction outside of Bulgaria and Poland. There was a marked reduction in the use of electricity, which some 30% of participating householders rely for heating. This demonstrates perhaps the affordability issue as much as anything – with the Western Isles having the second-highest energy bills in Scotland during 2023¹⁸.

Table 14: Total Energy Consumption – Scotland, UK (kWh)

	Baseline data	Final Data	Energy Savings	Primary Energy Savings
Electricity	2,200,940	1,464,529	736,411	1,399,181
Heating oil	4,973,596	4,922,986	50,610	55,671
Natural gas	168,679	158,439	10,240	12,288
		Total	797,261	1,467,140

¹⁸ <https://www.dailyrecord.co.uk/lifestyle/money/highest-lowest-energy-bills-scotland-31511072>
 February 2024

9 Concluding remarks

The objective of report was to outline the ‘energy savings’ realised by the households participating in EnergyMeasures. The context of this project and local specificities meant that the approach to calculating the reduced energy demand had to be tailored to circumstances in each country. For some countries the task was relatively straightforward (*e.g.*, with easy access to invoicing data), for others it was more complex and time-consuming (*e.g.*, utilities going out of business, widespread use of *ad hoc* fuels, *etc.*).

For each of the seven focal countries¹⁹, a brief overview was presented of the energy poverty context, the most important sources of energy, significant energy-related challenges and a brief treatment of the characteristics of the types of buildings engaged, a detail of the reductions in energy consumption for the participating households.

Table 15 below summarises the reductions in primary energy consumption during the duration of the project. Across each of the participating countries, there were substantial reductions in both electrical and non-electrical thermal energy consumption, with average annualised primary energy savings across the project estimated at 4,091 kWh per household.

Table 15: Reductions in primary energy consumption (‘savings’) amongst the participating households

	Number households	Elec kWh/yr ²⁰	Gas kWh/yr ²¹	District Heat kWh/yr ²²	Other kWh/yr ²³	Total	Average annual saving kWh/household
BE	598	234,148	810,459			1,044,607	1,747
BG	723	4,441,064		2,565,599	70,575	7,077,238	9,789
IE	603	314,437	349,040		145,915	858,006	1,423
NL	403	155,067	542,731			697,798	1,732
MK	620	570,207				570,207	920
PL	450	437,797	2,943,327		892,547	4,273,671	9,497
UK	511	1,399,181	12,288		55,671	1,467,140	2,871
Total	3,908	9,098,572	4,706,459	2,565,599	1,164,708	15,988.667	4,091

Poland and Bulgaria registered the highest avoided energy consumption of the focal countries. In Bulgaria the project concentrated on householders living in multifamily residential buildings. This engagement

¹⁹ Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland, and United Kingdom

²⁰ Electricity converted to primary energy using coefficient of 1.9 detailed in Directive (EU) 2023/179, Article 31.

²¹ Natural gas converted to primary energy using a coefficient of 1.2.

²² District heating converted to primary energy using BG national coefficient 1.3 (Latöšov *et al.*, 2013).

²³ Default primary energy factor of 1.1 used for non-renewables (*e.g.*, coal) and 0.2 for renewables (*e.g.*, biomass).

included working with the homeowners²⁴ to develop the cooperation and agreement required to progress the renovation of these condominium buildings²⁵. The estimated energy savings are based on the modelled performance of the buildings once the renovations have been realised. The large energy savings recorded in Poland were based on actual consumption reductions as shown in calculations based on data from a large amount (c. 40%) of the participating households. These savings realised in the Polish households are a testament to the success of the action in the Bielsko-Biala area.

Of course, it is not possible to consider these reductions without acknowledging the impact of the global energy crisis (2021–present) caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine²⁶, which coincided with the period of the project. This energy unaffordability crisis led to a significant reduction in energy consumption across European Countries²⁷, and to a substantial extent can be said to be responsible for the observed fall in energy consumption amongst the participating households²⁸. The project also ran during a period of milder than usual weather during both the 2022/23 and 2023/24 heating seasons. The support provided through the EnergyMeasures²⁹ contributed to achieving energy consumption in the participating households within this wider context.

It is not possible (and arguably not logical) to try to distinguish the project's contribution to energy savings from the wider context economically and metrologically. The increases in price (and moreover the widespread discussion of increasing energy costs) served to 'motivate' (or indeed it could be said to frighten) householders, the warmer winters provided an opportunity for people to reduce their thermal energy consumption while maintaining at least some comfort, in this context initiatives such as EnergyMeasures provided householders with the knowledge and importantly the confidence to reduce their energy use in a structured manner.

²⁴ And their respective homeowner associations (HOAs).

²⁵ Condominium renovation projects face significant challenges due to the complex ownership structures and necessary involvement of HOAs.

²⁶ While the Russian aggression in Ukraine greatly exacerbated (and have served to prolong) the energy crisis, its origins lie in a combination of factors, including disrupted supply chains, bad weather, low investment coupled with increased demand caused by post-pandemic economic recovery (IEA, undated).

²⁷ Electricity demand in the EU for instance was 6.4% lower in 2023 compared to 2021 (Brown & Jones, 2024).

²⁸ The warmer winter in 2023 (compared to 1991-2020 average) also contributed to reduced heating demand during the period, or at least to making reduced heating demand less disagreeable to households (*Ibid.*).

²⁹ Tailored small energy measures and behaviour change advice

10 References

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